

DIFFERENT ARTISTIC IDEAS AND POSITION		Creative and Performing Arts Keywords: Art, Conceptual, Reflected, Reality, Global.
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Abstract

Different media outlets are merely a tool of artists for visualization of conceptual ideas of self-reflection, while the visual motif in conceptual discourse becomes metalanguage or visual text. Conceptual art is reflection and analytics in society or in the art system and is based on special procedures in artistic creation, while the artist introducing the visual language promotes his views as a general review. The art that speaks at this level is an instrument that is conscious of historical associates, which makes it look full of things that raises emotions, requires appreciation, art which does not address the transfigured metaphysical conscience, but investigates the conditions of earthly existence and hence provokes to see things in a new way. The concept of art is formulated itself at the time and place where it is lived, as a result of its special intensity for modern philosophy and art, new ways are needed to reflect on this intensive realit that we live in. Art history as the most original tension of language through an external reality, unprecedented in a simple chronicle, but rather in a range of meaningful events, becomes the divided boundary between many types of art. Personal stories and experiences that are in fact the stories and experiences of others gain metavisual reflection. Art is used not only to put a problem on art itself but also on the art system, meaning the world. A non-marvelous description of the "global" scene in the troubles with the developed world will put many creative creators virtually anywhere between the ecstasy of catastrophe and terror; given their contexts: ethnic, religious, linguistic, temperamental, neurotic.

Introduction

The physical and cultural environment influences the behavior often to see and understand who we are in relation to where we live. Artists have different views of the "world", and they interpret the contextual-artistic circumstances of particular cultural situations, and on that basis, these artists redirect their motivations to contemporary reactions, such as the threat of environmental destruction; or multimedia technology applications in extreme proportions, the next example. In order to build, draw attention, and formulate how many moments were lived in a nearly spiritual connection with the environment is an attempt for these young artists. The emergence of these artworks does not want to promote any direction or stream, nor any inclusive situation; rather, it aspires to show the accessibility within the artistic context in a constant influx of reconfigurations and shifts of cultural values or different references. One of the goals is to accept the arts in order to be able to take our part in the field of contemporary discussion that is "done today in the world". Conceptual art is reflection and analytics in society or in the art system and is based on special procedures in artistic creation, while the artist introducing the visual language promotes his views as a general review. The “NE” exhibition as the first exhibition of young artists organized at the National Gallery of Kosovo (2002) has brought this exhibition to new artists. They as a group, and each one individually were introduced with a new energy thus testifying that the art of Kosovo will have a future and a prospect, that it is going with time.

The desire of these young people was to create valuable works and to have even the best presentations of their art. The exhibition offered different approaches and values, from the most tradicional to new forms of expression. But these natural differences for contemporary art are not

even distinctive differences. All of them were representatives of a generation that reflected real-world problems and the environment, with a similar or very similar feeling to social processes, and their reflection on visual arts. The concept of the exhibition was in line with this sensibility of the new art created in the world, as the project is supportive of quality art in the traditional media of expression, as well as for any kind of novelty and experiment.⁴

Zeni Ballazhi
*Smile of fake life, installation, 2002*⁵

... Anger towards reality is getting worse. The message given through a skull of an ox with a royal crown, on a black background on the white of a wall, will not need to be commented; it is enough to read the contrasts and the treacherous appearance of the skull of the ox under the false crown of splendor ... not worth a smile either.

To deliver figuratively social messages, an emotionally warm art, or to structure a more organic matter of everyday life, the artists introduced a new concept that renders valuable art and material to ordinary artworks. One step further gave to this direction the organization of the next exhibition "JU" 2003 at the National Gallery of Kosovo.

Creations or works of artists seem to fully formalize the existence of contemporary art on Kosovo's land. The "JU" exhibition was a different concept, idea and position. Here we are not dealing with new streams, but I would say with new influences in our art, which come as a result of the movement of artists around the world. The art of this group appears as opposed to the

⁴ Artistët e së nesërmes, 2002, 2

⁵ Ekspozita "Portreti" ne GKK, 2002

previous art. The "JU" concept was, in general, a powerful provocation and through it, these artists expand the idea of art. Through art-installations of young creators present interesting and typical positions of the new artistic scene. The artists used a common artistic approach, which is conceptual, where in an art-installation the idea is more important than its physical appearance, focusing more on the intellect than on the picture. At this moment the artist benefits from the audience and the audience from the artist.

ALBANIANS IN THE BALKANS OR THE BALKANS IN EUROPE, installation, 2008⁶

Perhaps the trend, therefore, to look at art as a convenience is also a tough reaction in recent years in the Balkans and in the world. However, the relationship between the work and the concept is quite organic, where there is an acceptable tendency and a tendency to expand the dimension of contemporary art in the Balkans. Moreover, this individual feature of these young artists at some exhibitions greatly increased the interest of visitors. This position characterizes an organization, surveyed preparation of the works of these artists in a very good way, offering us a wide variety of forms, greetings and infinite unknowns where expression and space are expressed. The only evaluation criterion for the next day in these presentations was the artistic accomplishment and their appearance in the world of contemporary art.⁷

The Idea that Art Transforms and Modifies

This concept tends to create full spaces in support of young artists who, with their fantasy and visual intelligence, sensitivity and provocative emotion, will exhibit contemporary art towards a new reality as a new grouped artistic relationship in the exhibition, where they will also have a

⁶ Cataclysm and Creativity, Art in an Age of Uncertainty, Contemporary Art Museum Skopje, Macedonia, 2008

⁷ Ekspozita JU, 2003, 2

chance to publish and the opportunity to offer the latest news in their art. We focused our judgment on the special presentation at some exhibitions. The exhibitions "Tomorrow Artists", "International M.Mulliçi Prize" organized by the National Gallery of Kosovo and the "International Award ONUFRI" organized by the Tirana National Art Gallery since the post-war years in Kosovo and after the communist regime in Albania echoed the most prominent efforts of artists to find new ways of coming to tomorrow that was hoped to unify one day with the great world of contemporary art and be at the same time a homage to all those efforts that have been made for the birth and keeping alive of this hope since the creation of art to this day. Artists departed from this awareness by accepting to work through specific language of art, but also trying to advertise this specificity as a project of transforming reality and implying art as a model of alternative behavior, hence knocking on the doors of the world great art and experienced artists. These not only proposed their experience as help in the first steps of new colleagues, but also welcomed new experiences. The field of activity is surrounded by the area of the language used, such as "art as art". The works placed on these exhibitions were powerful metaphors of this reality that we live with intensity. The wish of the artists participating in these editions for tomorrow was to make a presentation as specific and as close as possible to the visible and liked artistic values.⁸ What united these exhibited projects was the visual participation in the problems of urban territory, where authors' creative intelligence has converged through many original findings that make up the peculiarities of these exhibits. Artists there are part of the disciplinary problem; they use the visual tools to constantly emancipate the society they live in, and this is a new form of discipline. This phenomenon of many artists is considered a violation of public space movement, personal information abuse, and many other cases which we may call forms of public discipline. In the authenticity and individualism of the Balkan culture intervenes the European mentality, where the affirmation of the individual arises from the assurance of a reconciliation and adaptation to a standardized life model. To better illustrate this photography, some artists set between themselves and the world the diaphragm of the film camera and photo camera, which through the lens enabled the disposal of any individual display, of any suspicion of privacy for the individual. What is highlighted is the stereotyped gesture, made public as such and destined for consumption. Public space as a time utilization of the environment where a spatial coil was built follows the harmony, proportion and symmetry, dimensions that are metaphysically inhabitable not from man but from its shadow. Interfering in public spaces that are overseen by new surveillance tools, the artist has developed a work of dimensioning and reducing natural space, using new tools offered by contemporary technology, as a requirement at the beginning of the era of technology.

The actions of this intervention in the public space of the city remain anchored in the value of improvisation that wants to resist systematic and standardized living, a ray of immediate freedom. Within this poetry, there is also the anthropology of the individual, the art that keeps in touch with clean and painless spaces, which by its intervention modifies nature. Interventions are realized through the contemporary technological tools of these artists where they are coping with

⁸ Artistët e së nesërmes, 2007, 4

the amount of space to be faced and a touch is made, an experience with a clean and free space from any conditionality, from all sensory accidents to life.

*Everyone oversees man; Everyone is overseen by man; Every supervision is supervised by man.*⁹

Today, social systems are under tremendous stress. This change will be planted and will grow by conceptually influencing many new creators using the technology and the media that we will have the opportunity to present even in the coming years where the media structure can contribute significantly to the democratization of society, changing content and streamlining the media. Including various cultural concepts, audiovisual technologies, abstract art, technological network, computer science, nanotechnology, physics and scientific materials. Modern day people spend most of their time in a sort of virtual reality. The Internet has evolved into what is called a giant global mind ... The physical and cultural environment affects our behavior and influences to see and understand who we are in relation to the country we live in. Social and environmental restraint as a historical passage is preserved in memory and is today exposed to see others and preserve selfishness in remembrance. Accepting the data of this reality is transformed into conceptual data that sums up a physical amount of space, cleansing it of all the sensory, affective, hearing, and smelly accidents we are usually in contact with, leading it to the phenomenological conditioning of a coil which reinforces, simply because of the self-isolation, the psycho-sensual perception of the spectator. Nature is organized into a ritual lecture devoted to the community, where the natural element is transformed into a liberation of the incoherent and social use.

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